

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING MODERN INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING THE SUBJECT ECONOMICS OF NATURAL RESOURCES AND ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION

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Abstract. *This article discusses the importance of using modern innovative pedagogical technologies in teaching the subject of economics of natural resources and the environment, the development of science and technology at a very high pace, which requires the use of modern, innovative, advanced technologies in the process of teaching the subject.*

Keywords: *economics, reforms, higher education institutions, innovation, modern technologies, pedagogy, monitoring, natural resources, environment.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The main goal of the reforms carried out in the higher education system is aimed at informatization of education, that is, the introduction of information and communication technologies. The decree adopted on February 7, 2017 at the initiative of President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev in the Action Strategy for five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 - a radical improvement in the quality of general education, in-depth study of foreign languages, computer science and other important and demanding subjects, such: like mathematics, physics, chemistry and biology. It is aimed at solving current problems, such as stimulating scientific and innovative activities, creating effective mechanisms for introducing scientific and innovative achievements into practice.

At the same time, in the Action Strategy for five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period 2017-2021, strengthening macroeconomic stability and maintaining high rates of economic growth, aimed at further development and liberalization of the national economy, increasing the competitiveness of the economy, modernizing and accelerating the development of agriculture, continue institutional and structural reforms, reduce state participation in the economy, protect private property rights and further strengthen its priority position, stimulate the development of small businesses, business and private entrepreneurship, socio-economic development of regions, districts and cities on an integrated and proportionate basis, active attracting foreign investment into industries and regions of the economy of our country by improving the investment environment planned for five years (2017–2021). The first Action Strategy was adopted in 2017.

At the beginning of 2022, the President approved the development strategy of New Uzbekistan until 2026. According to the resolution, within the framework of the new strategy, “it is necessary to ensure the achievement of all goals that have not lost their relevance, as well as the implementation of current tasks specified in the development strategy of New Uzbekistan.”

The adoption of the new Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan by popular vote in a referendum held on April 30, 2023, served to strengthen the constitutional foundations for the creation of New Uzbekistan. The presidential elections were held in accordance with the new

Constitution. This is once again evidence of the political maturity of our society and the full support of our people for the reforms being implemented towards the creation of a New Uzbekistan.

The President approved the Uzbekistan 2030 strategy. Its goals include creating opportunities for all citizens to realize their potential, raising a healthy and educated generation, building a strong economy and ensuring justice, the rule of law and security. Shavkat Mirziyoyev, by his decree, approved the strategy “Uzbekistan - 2030”. According to the document, it was developed “based on the experience and results of public discussion during the implementation of the New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan.”

II. MAIN PART

When teaching economic sciences, including the science of economics of natural resources and the environment, in higher educational institutions where economic education is carried out, students gain a deeper mastery of the sciences, while explaining the role and importance of science in the development of the country's economy. Of great importance in their conservation is the effective and rational use of natural resources and the use of modern, innovative pedagogical technologies. Currently, science and technology are developing at a very high pace, which requires the use of modern, innovative, advanced technologies in the teaching of economic sciences. Every teacher working in the higher education system to educate young people who are the future of the country, highly educated, highly cultural, highly qualified personnel, must diligently fulfill the task assigned to him, take his profession seriously, and love it. This and, realizing that he is a responsible person in his field, there is an urgent issue of increasing the effectiveness of the lesson, the effective use of modern technologies that are being developed to improve the quality and efficiency of education. In our country, it is of fundamental importance to develop in every person the knowledge, skills, and abilities to create and manage new pedagogical information technologies. Informatization of the education system creates opportunities for further strengthening economic and social knowledge, improving the quality of education with the help of modern information technologies, and facilitating human adaptation to different social environments.

Development of modern pedagogical and information technologies and methods of teaching economic subjects, ensuring the full assimilation of knowledge, skills and qualifications in the education system, based on innovative technologies for teaching these subjects, lectures, discussions, design of practical classes and use in teaching activities, development in teaching subjects of this direction. Currently, one of the important directions for accelerating the educational process in higher educational institutions is the individualization of training and the development of the creative abilities of future specialists. To do this, it is necessary to introduce new forms and methods of teaching, organize the integration of the educational process with scientific production, and create new effective forms of organizing students' independent learning.

Equipping universities with modern technical means, information and communication technologies, cameras, classroom monitors and educational laboratory equipment is an important tool for increasing the knowledge potential and efficiency of students, and in turn, additional responsibility is assigned to teacher educators. A modern teacher is required not only to know his subject perfectly, but also to have the necessary knowledge and skills in using modern technical means, and at the same time he must be an encyclopedist and perfectly answer all students' questions. Based on the above, all teachers working in the higher education system should continue

to improve traditional teaching methods, consistently apply and develop new pedagogical innovative technologies in the teaching of economic sciences, and develop them. It is important to keep up with the times of teaching methods.

In many cases, the lecture method is used in teaching environmental and natural resource sciences, and this method reduces the activity of some students in the lesson, and it is difficult to attract the audience's attention to the topic and understand the technical processes involved. Nowadays, the use of more information and communication technologies in presenting and explaining the topic will improve and enhance the effectiveness of teaching and it is time to study the best practices of countries.

By constantly increasing literacy in the use of innovative technologies in all layers of our society, we will develop human capital in the field of information technology, improve the system of training and advanced training, primarily through in-depth acquisition of knowledge in the field of information technology in the field of modern information communications, Internet and digital technologies.

III. Discussion

Saved To take education to a new level, it is necessary to use various innovative technologies that make the student an active participant in the educational process. Innovation translated from English as “innovation” means innovation, invention. Funds spent on the economy to ensure replacement of technologies and technological generations; innovations in the field of engineering, technology, management and labor organization based on scientific and technical achievements and best practices, as well as their use in various fields and fields of activity.

Today, due to a significant restructuring of the quality and content of education, the introduction of new innovative technologies, the approach to organizing the educational process has changed, the need to intensify the cognitive activity of students has increased, the introduction of new innovative technologies makes the educational process more effective, provides students with new means, methods and sources of educational material. To further improve the educational activities of students using innovative technologies, basic knowledge of modern information technologies and the technical capabilities of communication technologies are required; students must acquire skills in using information resources and independent work using modern computer technologies. The introduction of innovative technologies into the educational environment significantly increases the efficiency of educational activities by automating information processing and calculations that form an understanding of the essence of educational material. The continuous search for the introduction of innovative technologies into the educational process and increasing the effectiveness of education is becoming the need of the day. The introduction of new methods into the educational process is one of the tasks facing teachers. In addition to providing other information during the lesson, if the teacher shows additional information on the Internet, multimedia programs, tables, etc., this increases the interest of students, but also helps students form their independent study at the required level and master the topic as fully as possible.

IV. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we can say that in teaching the subject economics of natural resources and environmental protection, it is aimed at increasing students' knowledge, encouraging students to independent, free thinking, research activities, a creative approach to each issue, a sense of responsibility, analysis, and most importantly, motivate students. This increases his interest in his chosen profession.

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